

erythrinae, *Hemicycliophora* sp., *Hemicriconemoides* spp., *Hirschmanniella oryzae*, *Hoplolaimus* sp., *Pratylenchus* sp., and *Tylenchorhynchus* spp. The most important are *H. erythrinae*, *H. oryzae*, *Hoplolaimus*, and *Tylenchorhynchus*. *H. oryzae* is widely distributed and abundant. During feeding it moves in the root system of the host plant and dissolves its cell walls, forming large cavities that affect the efficient

functioning of the root system during heavy infestations. The population of this nematode increases with increasing age of the standing crop.

Hoplolaimus sp. occurs in comparatively low numbers. It damages the parenchymatous cells, which retards plant growth. *Tylenchorhynchus* spp., and *H. erythrinae* are widely distributed in Pakistan but have variable populations. They damage mostly the cortex,

therefore their feeding has less impact than that of other species. White tip disease of rice caused by *Aphelenchoides besseyi* has not been recorded in Pakistan, but it is widespread elsewhere.

Nematode damage seems to depend on the population, intra- and inter-specific competition, reproductive rates, and environmental factors. Exact losses caused by nematodes in Pakistan's paddy crop are not known.

Rice hispa found on wheat in the Punjab, India

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The rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* causes considerable damage to rice in parts of Gurdaspur, Amritsar, Hoshiarpur, and Kapurthala districts in Punjab state, India. The insect breeds actively from

May to October, then overwinters, probably in the adult stage.

In early March 1978, rice hispa attacked the wheat cultivar WG 357 at the Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala. The overall damage was not serious; from 3 to 6 adults/10 m² were recorded. By the end of March, the insect also appeared in the summer rice nursery; 2 to 4 adults/seedling were observed. During the off-season, a limited survey of wild grasses and weeds at the research station showed no rice

hispa. A more detailed and extensive survey is needed to establish the insect's overwintering habits.

The finding of rice hispa on wheat is especially significant in the Punjab, where rice and wheat are generally rotated. If the insect can establish on wheat as well as on rice, it may become more serious because food material will be available to it year round. Efforts to grow two crops of rice per year may further accentuate the hispa problem.

A new enemy of *Azolla*

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The aquatic fern *Azolla pinnata* is being recommended for incorporation into rice fields as a natural source of fertilizer. Its cultivation is gaining momentum among rice farmers because of its ability to fix

atmospheric nitrogen symbiotically with blue-green algae. *Azolla* is estimated to fix from 30 to 35 kg N/ha within 20 days.

Studies at the College of Agriculture, Vellayani, show that such pests as lepidopterous larvae and snails (gastropoda) are major factors limiting *Azolla* propagation. The phytophagous gastropods damage the fern more severely than the caterpillars do.

The snails feed voraciously on the fern at the edge of the paddy, close to the water surface. They sometimes move to the water just below the floating *Azolla* and devour the fern, but do not feed on rice plants. The pest spreads fairly rapidly.

Phorate (10 G) applied at the recommended dosage of 12.5 kg/ha for insect control also controlled the snails.

Outbreak of rice caseworm and brown planthopper in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India

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The rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*, previously a minor rice pest in the Periyar Vaigai River Project of Tamil Nadu, assumed major importance in single-cropped areas of Madurai district

in December 1977. The high yielding variety IR20 is widely grown in those tracts. The planting season usually begins in September and October. Infestation was severe in rice that was transplanted later. Patches of cut and scraped leaf surfaces and withered plants were prominent.

The brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, which was earlier considered a minor pest in that area, has become serious since the introduction of high yielding dwarf varieties such as IR8 and

IR20. Infestation was heavy in 1973 and 1974. It was also severe in several parts of Melur and Vellalore in December 1977. The varieties IR20 and Bhavani were infested in the flowering and maturity stages and severely hopperburned. The outbreak may have been caused by the introduction of fertilizer-responsive, high-tillering rice varieties; heavy fertilizer applications; closer plant spacings; and indiscriminate use of pesticides.